

D8.2 - DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN

StretchBio – Continuous two-dimensional Stretch monitoring of fresh tissue Biopsies.

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Document author(s):

Entity	Contributor
ReadyCell	Alexandre Cabré
UB-IN2UB	Albert Romano-Rodríguez, Francisco Hernández-Ramírez
All	Contributions from the consortium partners

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable establishes the basis for the development of common dissemination, communication, and exploitation plans in StretchBio, and overviews the activities completed during the first year of the project.

The here-presented contents are dynamic and set out strategies to support a sustainable uptake of project results by end-users as well as identifies in detail stakeholders, actions, tools, materials, KPIs and procedures. What is being written in the deliverable is alive and will be updated when necessary, according to project needs, even after its formal delivery to the EC.

Further details will be provided in future WP8-deliverables (*D8.3 – Report on dissemination and training actions, D8.4 – Report on communication and outreach, and D8.5 – Patent portfolio and updated exploitation plan*) as well as the periodic Project Reports.

The overall goal of StretchBio is the design, fabrication, and proof of application of advanced compact nanosystems for the continuous label-free ex vivo monitoring and fast quantification of two-dimensional mechanical stresses induced by fresh tumour samples upon their treatment with drugs aiming to rescue normal tissue elasticity. These devices shall be used in personalized medicine. In this context, WP8 aims at increasing the project impact through concrete exploitation actions and wide dissemination of the results to society and interested stakeholders.

During the first 12 months of the project, the WP leader (ReadyCell), supported by the project partners, has established proper mechanisms and methods to valorise and spread all non-confidential results to the identified target groups. In particular, dissemination and communication materials have been created; defining project identity and establishing adequate project visibility, despite the attained results being still in their infancy.

From M13 to M36, a new phase of the dissemination and exploitation plan will be launched to engage target audience groups in a more active way. Finally, the capitalization of StretchBio results will start from M37 until the end of the project. During this latter stage, mechanisms to ensure long-lasting visibility and impact of the project outcomes are set up.

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Framework Programme
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
SME	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprise
WP	Work Package

2 Objectives and Approach

The main purpose of the here-presented “*Dissemination and Exploitation Plan*” is to promulgate the project outputs to key stakeholders and thus create added-value within the target communities and initiatives in Europe.

As defined in the GA, the objectives of WP8 are:

- Defining and implementing effective strategies of exploitation of StretchBio results & managing IP.
- Maintaining regular contact with end-users, and other related-projects.
- Organizing workshops and short-term missions.
- Planning scientific publications, presentations, and organization of conferences.
- Organizing online communication and outreach activities.

Therefore, this plan is divided into two complementary activities:

- Dissemination and communication activities;** oriented to show the attractiveness of the achieved results and their impact towards a target audience composed of key stakeholders, and the general public (society).
- Exploitation actions;** to establish the main pillars for a future market uptake plan of the most promising and mature results generated by the project. The exploitation strategy identifies technical choices towards the most promising directions, thus maximizing the opportunities for innovation and business.

The consortium is committed to ensure that the dissemination materials prepared for the promotion of the research results and benefits will not compromise the interests of the industrial stakeholders before disclosure.

The Dissemination and Communication strategy of StretchBio combines online and offline channels and tools, so the message is reinforced and assured to reach the identified audiences. The findings from the StretchBio project will be then tailored to the specific audiences needs and provide a basis for fostering public support.

Target Audience and Beneficiaries

Four target groups have been identified as the main recipients of the here presented actions:

Target Groups	Communication Channels	Aim
Scientific and academic community	Communications in congresses, articles, scientific publications, and assistance in specialized sessions	Disseminate the results obtained from the project to establish synergies with other researchers and share experiences. Scientific impact.
Oncology research centres, oncology hospitals and patient associations	Outreach events, specialized sessions, and newsletter	Establish alliances to make oncology researchers and clinicians aware of the progress of the project as well as the

		possibilities that the device can offer them. Awareness impact.
Pharma industry and investors	EIC events, investment events	Evaluate the possibility to transfer the results to the market. Exploitation impact.
General population	Outreach events, social media, media appearances, press releases and website	Make people aware of the advances in biomedical research towards personalized medicine

Table 1 - Target audiences and beneficiaries from the dissemination, communication and exploitation actions

Synergies Between Project Partners

The following table summarizes the main strengths and contributions from the partners to the implementation of the here-proposed plan:

Partner	Partners Type	Contribution
LEITAT	Research Centre	Great capacity to approach several industry sectors, including client networks and commercialization channels. Main activity will focus on identifying and engaging potential customers interested in product/services generated.
RCELL	SME	Attract new clients and reinforce the loyalty of the customer portfolio thanks to the new competitive advantages acquired in terms of boosting current products/services with new solutions. Main activity will focus on providing the industrial perspective to an academic consortium.
UB, DTU, ALU-FR	University	Engage the scientific and industrial communities across Europe to raise awareness about the project and contribute to knowledge generation. Generate new research lines and training programs aligned with the key pillars of the excellence in science established in H2020 and Horizon Europe. Involvement of research groups and communication departments in dissemination activities. Main activity will focus on attaining scientific breakthroughs and achieve a significant awareness of project results by the society.

Table 2 – Partners' contributions to the dissemination, communication and exploitation actions

Consortium Working Group

To ease the internal communication within the consortium regarding the dissemination and exploitation of the project results, a dedicated working group has been created. Regular meetings are organized to facilitate an effective and proactive activities.

The working group members are listed below:

Institution	Contact people	Email
READYCELL	Àlex Estivill	aestivill@readycell.com
UB-IN2UB	Pol Romano, Francisco Hernández and Albert Romano	pol.romano@ub.edu, fhernandezra@ub.edu, albert.romano@ub.edu

UB-IBUB	Florenci Serras and Montserrat Corominas	fserras@ub.edu, mcorominas@ub.edu
UB-Biomedicina	Jordi Alcaraz and Patricia Fernández	jalcaraz@ub.edu, pfernandezn@ub.edu
DTU	Winnie E. Svendsen, Christian Vinter Bertelsen and Maria Dimaki	wisv@dtu.dk, cvbe@dtu.dk, madi@dtu.dk
ALU	Katrin Schmitt	katrin.schmitt@imtek.uni-freiburg.de
LEITAT	Imma Prats and Xavier Ponte	iprats@leitat.org, xponte@leitat.org

Table 3 – Dissemination and exploitation working group within StretchBio

In view of future interactions with external stakeholders, a dedicated e-mail account has already been generated: communications@stretchbio.eu

Key Dissemination and Communication Channels and Activities

StretchBio has generated dedicated channels and activities to disseminate and communicate the project outputs to the selected groups of interest. Prior to that, the consortium worked on visual guidelines to provide external consistent appearance, and the guidelines to manage the new data and intellectual property. Further information on these aspects is provided below:

Visual Guidelines

The very first action launched after the start of the project was to create a recognizable brand of StretchBio which reflects the main goals of the initiative and offers the audience/stakeholders a clear identification of the values and message. This has resulted in concrete visual guidelines and project templates (i.e., deliverables, presentations), which are available as an annex to this deliverable (Annex I).

Logo

The project logo has been conceived by a professional designer, and agreed on by the partners, with the intent to be easily recognizable and meaningful for the identified audience, thus it represents the official “trademark” of the project.

The official version of the logo is the coloured version, but two monochrome variants have also been developed (one in black and one in white) to facilitate the use in cases where the background does not allow the use of the coloured one.

The logo tries to represent the device that will be developed in the project so that the three elements that make up the image correspond to the silicon pillars (the blue square), the light beam (the light blue line) and the cellular tissue (the orange circle).

Preliminary Considerations

Data Management

StretchBio has conceived a Data Management Plan (DMP) to support the management life cycle for all data, in the broadest sense, which are generated, collected and processed by the project.

The DMP has been structured following the guideline of the H2020 programme on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020¹ including the following information:

- Data Management Plan (DMP) guiding principles and strategy
- Description of StretchBio type of data
- Introduction to FAIR DATA
- Allocation of resources
- Data Security
- Ethical Aspects
- Conclusions

The DMP is an official project Deliverable (D7.2) which was due in month 6, but it is periodically updated throughout the project implementation, when necessary. The first initial version will evolve as a function of the research activity and the feedback received from the EC and other significant project stakeholders.

Obligation to Disseminate Results

All H2020-funded projects must disseminate as much information as possible. On top of that, the StretchBio project participates in the “Open Research Data Pilot” (ORPD), which means that all partners are committed to giving open access to all data generated during the project unless it goes against the consortium’s legitimate interests.

As far as data are concerned, the consortium rationale to use research results will accommodate the diagram shown below (Figure 1).

Each data set created during the project will be assessed and categorized as open, embargoed, or restricted by the owners of the content. The project coordinator and if necessary, the Steering Committee², will closely monitor the process to guarantee a homogeneous approach to the decision-making process.

All the data sets, regardless of their categorization, will be stored in each of the participating entities' databases.

Among all project datasets, deliverables and associated documentation, the following categories of the project outputs are already declared as ORPD and as a consequence, they will be made, as a rule, “Open Access” (to be provided free of charge for public sharing):

- Project deliverables labelled as public in the Grant Agreement
- Articles published in Open Access scientific journals
- Conference and Workshop abstracts/articles

¹ H2020 templates: Data management plan v1.0 – 13.10.2016

² Body as defined in the project consortium agreement

Figure 1 - Decision-making process for the categorization of data generated by StretchBio

Open Access to Scientific Publications

As said before, StretchBio consortium is committed to making the project data FAIR whenever possible. As far as scientific publications are concerned, priority shall be given to high-rank scientific journals from the participating disciplines.

Keeping this in mind, Green Open Access will be the preferred formula to disseminate the project results, but the editorial policy of well-known journals, such as Nature, Science, ..., might force the consortium to opt for Gold Access in some particular cases. The fees associated with the publication of “Gold” papers have already been foreseen in the project budget. The cost-sharing, in the case of multiple authors, shall be decided among the authors on a case-by-case basis.

Green and Gold manuscripts will be freely available in the Zenodo-project dedicated site (see next section) as well as curated and preserved in the institutional repositories of UB, DTU and ALU-FR following the provisions of the standard policies of these academic partners.

Open Access to Research Data

Each data set created during the project will be assessed and categorized as open, embargoed, or restricted by the owners of the content. The project coordinator, and if necessary, the General Assembly, will closely monitor the process to guarantee a homogeneous approach to the decision-making process.

All the data sets, regardless of their categorization, will be stored in each of the participating entities' databases. In addition, those categorized as opened or embargoed will be publicly shared (in the case of embargo, after the period is over) through the ZENODO project site³. ZENODO is an open access repository for all fields of science that allows uploading any kind of data file format, which is recommended by the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE).

³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/stretchbio/?page=1&size=20>

Those data of particular interest for dissemination purposes will be published on the project website and the adequate social media channels. As this is being written, the first open materials are already available in ZENODO.

IP Rights Protection

To effectively manage the IP generated during the project implementation, the participants have signed a consortium agreement based on DESCA model. As a rule of thumb, background and results are owned by the party that brings or generates them, unless joint-developments are completed, which will make necessary the agreement of all the involved actors.

The consortium has a real commitment to exploit the results without losing sight of the eminent scientific character of most of the partners. For this reason, the industrial expertise of ReadyCell is deemed crucial, since they are expected to guide the Participants in concrete exploitation actions beyond the mere publication of results in scientific journals. This will be further developed in the coming years of the project, once tangible results are achieved.

Communication Channels

Website

StretchBio website is hosted on <https://stretchbio.eu/> and is available in the English language. It is administrated by UB-IN2UB with the support of ReadyCell. Launched in October 2021, the StretchBio website will be operative for the whole duration of the project and at least until August 2026, a year after the completion of the grant agreement tasks. The website is updated with news, links, and events generated by the project activity and it provides direct access to the public material hosted at ZENODO. For further information, please refer to the deliverable D8.1.

Social Media Guidelines

StretchBio has also a Twitter account (<https://twitter.com/StretchBio>) in which all the content generated by the project activity is regularly released. The aim is to reach as many people as possible beyond academia; the content of the publications is thought to facilitate the capture of general users' attention. The collaboration with the official accounts of the institutions that participate in the project is crucial once concrete outputs are released.

Communication Materials

The consortium is in the process of developing professional communication materials to promote the StretchBio project in different areas and to heterogeneous audiences. Within these materials, a leaflet and a roll-up with the main information of the project (objectives, work packages and expected outcomes) will be ready in the coming months. Once the development of the project evolves, infographics with preliminary results will be elaborated to present the results to specific stakeholders (i.e., scientific association or investors forums).

Reporting Events

Partners of the consortium will attend relevant events, conferences, workshops, and fairs of the sector. They should be actively involved in the general dissemination of StretchBio concept and seeking opportunities to present and showcase the project in both their countries and at both international levels. The participation in events must be previously authorised upon request by the consortium hierarchy in order to plan visible activities through communication channels, and align the activity with a meaningful IP protection strategy. The same approach applies for scientific publications.

Horizon2020 / Horizon Europe Support

The consortium is aware of the tools and bodies provided by the EU to improve the dissemination, communication and exploitation of Horizon2020 projects, such as the Horizon Results Booster (<https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>) and the EU Innovation Radar (<https://www.innoradar.eu/>).

In this sense, the Project Coordinator has established the first contact with Mr. Enrique CLAVEROL-TUNTURÉ, IC Programme Manager (PM) overseeing EIC projects in the area of Health – Medical Technologies and Medical Devices at EIC/EISMEA, in February 2022 to close monitor the project development and if possible, design a meaningful exploitation strategy of the new results. Both parties agreed that the project activity had to move forward so that the full potential of StretchBio can be evaluated.

As pointed out before, the StretchBio development is still in its infancy, and fundamental work is still ongoing. Once the first functional prototype is available, EU support will be actively searched.

3 Communication Tools and Actions

StretchBio is expected to generate a wide range of results, some of which will be publicly available according to the GA provisions. The following list summarizes the main project reports to be communicated to the identified target groups during the first year following a three-level strategy: online, offline, and physical dissemination.

Month	WP	Outputs	Status
6	2	D2.1 Report presenting the results of the simulated relation between nanopillar deformation and horizontally exerted forces based on finite element modelling.	Completed Public at ZENODO
9	3	D3.1 The complete fabrication route for the successful fabrication of the nanopillar arrays of different diameters, heights and pitches will be reported.	Completed Public at ZENODO except for a confidential annex
12	3	D3.2 Experimental data on the relation deformation-force for the nanopillar sizes and geometries as compared to those obtained from the simulation.	Delayed Public
12	4	D4.1 Viability tests of the cell survival upon prolonged contact with the nanopillar array, aiming to achieve biocompatible surfaces.	Completed Public at ZENODO
12	5	D5.1 Report on the design and fabrication issues of the optical grating both simulated and fabricated.	Completed Public at ZENODO

Table 4 – Technical deliverables labelled as public during the first year of StretchBio

Digital Marketing Strategy

Website

The project website will act as a dissemination hub, central repository, and news broadcast channel for all public information. It has been created with the specific aim to respond to the communication and dissemination needs of the project, which include:

- **Being dynamic** with all kinds of content being periodically updated, from technical articles, research papers and public deliverables, to pieces of news and policies of the sector, initiatives related to the European Commission, and events created by the project or other ones with complementary objectives.
- **Attracting more visitors** thanks to an improved positioning in engine searchers, while also sharing the content through social networks and newsletters.
- **Link building** to create synergies between the StretchBio website and the partners' websites, as well as with other relevant agents of the sector in the same field.
- **Responsive Web Design** to make the page available on all devices (desktops, tablets, and phones) and create a quick and intuitive user experience browsing the web.

The website is periodically updated throughout the project so that it will always present meaningful information for the interested stakeholders, including:

- **General information** about the project including objectives and work packages
- **Description of all the organization's members** of the consortium including the main technical staff involved in StretchBio
- **Latest news**, calendar of events organized within the framework of the project and press releases and other materials/resources focused on the Media.
- **Information about the results**, scientific papers, as well as infographics of the main results (link to Zenodo),
- **Newsletters**
- **Contact information** to the project participants

To increase the traffic to the StretchBio website, this will be SEO-friendly and respond to the following standards:

- **Keyword Optimization** for maximum searchability.
 - Biomedical research, lung cancer, silicon pillars, nanopillars, personalized medicine, fetopen, Horizon2020
- **Logical Content Organization** considering the European guidelines of best practices, to help visitors find other related content easily.
- **Content Promotion** to increase visibility of new content by sharing it on social networks and building internal and external links to such content.

Website visits and downloads are monitored using the JetPack plugin for WordPress.

Figures will be periodically shared with the Project Officer and external evaluators. GDPR provisions will be always considered.

Newsletter and Mailings

Newsletter and mailing campaigns will be launched at least on roughly yearly basis at months M14, M26, M36 and M48. E-newsletters are to be sent to the recipients' database consisting of the project audience.

The database will be nourished by a registration form included on the website, existing contact lists of the partners, and further additions when participating in other EU initiatives, events, fairs, workshops, etc.

The newsletter will be written in English, available both in HTML and PDF format, and it will be also available in the News & Events section on the project website. The document will include information on project activities, announcements of calls, conferences, events, and updates on relevant developments.

In addition, mailings with invitations to relevant workshops and webinars, consultations and other information which cannot wait for the newsletter publication or that cannot appear only in the newsletter will be sent out to the same database used for the newsletter distribution.

Each project participant will translate the document into the local languages (German, Danish, Spanish, and Catalan) to maximize the impact of the action.

Media Relations

To stimulate the interest in StretchBio activities and results, and to inform as much as possible StretchBio's target audience, press releases will be distributed during the project. At the launch of the project, a first press release was prepared and published on StretchBio website as well as on each partners' website with significant impact in the media.

The screenshot displays a press release from the University of Barcelona and the University of Freiburg. The top section features the University of Barcelona logo and navigation menu. The main text discusses the StretchBio project, a nanotechnology for customized treatment of solid tumors, led by Albert Romano. The bottom part shows the University of Freiburg logo and a project overview section for 'Continuous two-dimensional Stretch monitoring of fresh tissue Biopsy (StretchBio)'.

Figure 2 – Initial press released published by the University of Barcelona and the University of Freiburg

Future press releases will be prepared in parallel to the StretchBio most relevant events. To maximize the impact, the consortium will approach to the official channels set up by the EU.

Type	Channel	url
Portal	Project website	www.stretchbio.eu
Portal	Beneficiaries' websites	-
Portal	EIC website	eic.ec.europa.eu/news
Magazine	Horizon - The EU Research and Innovation Magazine	http://horizon-magazine.eu/
Magazine	Futuris and Innovation Magazine	https://www.euronews.com/next/next-series/futuris

Magazine	Research*EU Results Magazine	https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/en
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Table 5 – Channels for distribution of project press releases

Outreach Activities

Since the project aims at reaching the general audience (society in general), a set of activities will be progressively organized, seeking an active engagement and two-way communication. Outreach activities also feed content to the communication channels and tools (website, social media, newsletters, press releases, etc.), generating impact on different audiences.

During the first year of the project, the following initiative have already been confirmed, despite they will be done after M12.

Activity	Location	Dates	Description
European Researcher's Night	Barcelona	27 th of September to 2 nd of October 2022	<p>Presentation at the CosmoCaixa Barcelona science museum.</p> <p>The European Researcher's Night is an outreach activity co-funded by the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe, under the project NitRecercat.</p>
Science Week	Barcelona	11 th to 20 th of November 2022	<p>The Science is an outreach activity organised by FCRI (Catalan Foundation for Research and Innovation), with the support of the Ministry of Business and Knowledge of the Government of Catalonia and "la Caixa" Foundation.</p>

Table 6 – Outreach activities committed during the first year of the project

In the coming months, and once more tangible results are available, the outreach activities intensity will progressively increase: open days sessions at the participants' venues as well as dedicated sessions at the hospitals will be organized.

General presentation of the project at international events

International conferences, congresses, workshops, exhibitions, and fairs are the events in which the most effective dissemination and communication actions to reach the different stakeholders can be organized.

The participation in these events will generate more visibility for StretchBio project and will boost the contact with stakeholders and other European projects.

The table below shows the event in which the general concept of the project has been presented so far.

Name/Title of Event	Location	Dates	Type of Activity
Micro-Nanoengineering Conference	Leuven (Belgium)	September 2022	International conference

Table 7 – Events in which the StretchBio concept is presented (year 1)

Scientific Contributions – Publications & Conferences

As stated in both the GA and the deliverable D7.2 “Data Management Plan”, scientific outputs will be published in high-impact journals whenever possible. Open access will be guaranteed even by supporting “Gold Access” costs.

At the time being, no publications have been submitted to peer-reviewed journals yet, despite the consortium working on the first manuscript drafts.

On the other hand, participation in technical conferences and workshops is considered a crucial event to disseminate the project outputs to specialized audiences. In the table below, the participation of the consortium in international conferences is summarized⁴:

Conference	Venue	Title	Contribution
MRS Fall Meeting	Boston, Nov’21	Simulation and fabrication of a photonic force sensor based on silicon nanopillars	Oral
MNE 2022	Leuven, Sept’22	Photonic nanosystem for the continuous two-dimensional stretch monitoring of fresh tissue biopsies ⁵	Oral
MNE 2022	Leuven, Sept’22	Modelling the mechanical response of silicon nanopillars for the design of a biomedical force sensor	Poster
MNE 2022	Leuven, Sept’22	Performance comparison of a Bosch versus CORE process for etching silicon nanostructures	Poster

Table 8 – Participation in international conferences (year 1)

⁴ The criterium for MNE 2022 is the submission date of abstracts. The event will take place in September 2022.

⁵ General overview of StretchBio concept

4 KPI's and Monitoring

The Dissemination and Exploitation Plan sets up the framework to ensure the smooth management and effective implementation of the WP8 activities. In this sense, a set of KPIs has been established as benchmarks for evaluating the effectiveness and the impact of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities during the project implementation.

To this end, we will use different methods to assess the success of our initiatives, depending on the type of activity:

- **Website statistics:** Jetpack plugin to measure traffic to the website, time spent there, which sections are “stickiest” and how social media is driving traffic.
- **Social media impact** will be evaluated using Hootsuite reports, LinkedIn Company Page Analytics, and the Tweet Activity Dashboard.
- **Newsletter figures:** electronic newsletters come with their proprietary analytics, which will be used to measure the user’s engagement with the content, whether they opened the email, read it, clicked through the links, etc.
- **Contributions to events and conferences:** it will be measured as function of the number of technical contributions, potential audience and other specific figures such as the number of given leaflets, website traffic before and after events, changes in social media followers.

All these figures will be progressively reported to the EC and finally compiled in the deliverables D8.3 – “Report on dissemination and training actions” and D8.4 – “Report on communication and outreach”.

In the table below, tangible KPIs for the entire project as well as the figures for the first year of the project are given⁶. These values will be used to monitor how the plan effectiveness evolves until the end of the project.

Area / Activity	Metrics	KPI at M48	Value at M12	%	Rationale
Website	Visitors	1.000	64	6%	Dissemination metrics are not linear and depend to a large extent on the progress of the project. From month 12, the number of publications in the different media will increase and the percentage of achievement will increase quickly
	Views	25.000	534	2%	
Social Networks	Posts	160	6	4%	
	Followers	300	10	3%	
	Visits	25.000	1.255	6%	
	Interactions	500	24	5%	
Open material / data	Subscriptions to newsletter	80	0	0%	Option not opened in the website yet

⁶ For the first year of the project, most of the KPI figures are not representative since the project activity has been progressively activated

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	Number of downloads from ZENODO	1.000	49	5%	Figures on August 28 th 2022
Announcements on partners' websites, Press releases campaign, publication of articles	Scientific publications	12	0	0%	Manuscripts under preparation
	Press releases	4	1	25%	-
	News published in the project website	40	4	10%	-
Participation in the media (TV, radio)	Appearances/Interviews released	2	0	0%	No activity until having tangible results
Participation in relevant events	Conferences and workshops attended (individual contributions)	50	4	8%	-
	General project presentations done	12	1	8.5%	-
	Synergies established with stakeholders	5	0	0%	-
Outreach	Activities	20	2	10%	-
	Participants (total)	5.000	-	-	Not calculated until the end of September 2022
Exploitation	Participation in EU initiatives	3	1	33%	Monitoring by the Medical Technologies and Medical Devices at EIC/EISMEA
	Protected results	5	0	0%	No activity until having tangible results

Table 9 – Dissemination, communication and exploitation KPIs (entire project and Y1)

5 Exploitation Strategy

According to article 28 of the GA, each beneficiary must take measures to ensure the exploitation of its results up to four years after the end of the project. Thus, an initial exploitation strategy will be defined not just at a project consortium scale but also at an individual partner level.

The overall goal of the StretchBio project is the design, development, fabrication, and proof of application of an advanced label-free and compact nanosystem for the continuous monitoring and quantification of mechanical stresses in ex vivo fresh tissue biopsies. This nanodevice will allow testing of the changes of these tissues upon their treatment with anticancer drugs for improved drug screening.

StretchBio's exploitation strategy aims to maximize and expand the project objectives:

- Making an impact in the study of tissue growth and drug screening in solid tumours, which ultimately leads to personalized medicine and the development of ad-hoc treatments.
- Solving the unmet need for monitoring cellular mechanical properties in small tissue biopsies like those obtained with core needles.
- Creating an advanced label-free and compact nanodevice for the continuous monitoring and quantification of mechanical stresses in ex-vivo fresh tissue biopsies.
- Supporting the wide dissemination of findings from the project by publishing open access scientific articles and presenting project results in key scientific conferences.
- Organizing specific workshops, meetings, and seminars as well as using media to capture the interest of potential stakeholders.
- Analysing the project results and prototypes for potential development (roadmap).
- Performing feasibility studies on the possibility to launch products or services, including mapping of existing or under development technologies.
- Expanding the network of contacts in pathology anatomy and oncology departments of hospitals and drug screening and personalized medicine companies, among others, for the development of future collaborations.
- Establishing direct contact with industry working on the field of drug screening and personalized medicine.

The Exploitation Methodology

The main objective of the exploitation strategy is to turn project outcomes into benefits, favouring and helping project partners to launch new activities and businesses. Depending on the partner, these benefits can be both financial and/or non-monetary.

ReadyCell, as Exploitation Manager, will design an exploitation methodology customized to the nature and size of the StretchBio consortium and consider fast-track implementation. This methodology is based on a step-by-step approach that defines a clear exploitation roadmap. It has been presented to all partners, and a solid commitment from the consortium in terms of active participation and involvement will be sought immediately after the 12-month review meeting of the project. The following figure illustrates the methodology expected to apply:

Figure 3 - Exploitation Methodology to be implemented after M12

The Exploitation Timeline

The exploitation methodology will be implemented amid the StretchBio project development, intensifying the efforts once the results are more consistent and technologically mature. This scenario is expected to occur in the first year (M12) with a clear escalation during year two.

Identification of Key Results

All key results generated in the development of the technical WPs will be summarised and classified according to their expected exploitable potential in the table below which will be periodically updated to reflect the latest developments of the project.

Exploitable Result	Type of IP	Owner(s)

Table 10 - Expected exploitable results (table template)

Evaluation of Prototype's Business and Innovation Potential

Besides evaluating the exploitability of all key results, barriers to any application of the prototype will also be investigated, including:

- Inadequate financing
- Skills shortages
- Regulation that hinders innovation
- IPR issues
- Incompatibility between parts of systems (lack of standards)
- Mismatch between market needs and the solution

Business Model Assessment

A business model generation strategy will be created based on Lean Canvas and complemented with focus tools.

A detailed market plan will also be completed, including SWOT and PESTLE analysis of:

- Industry challenges
- Market maturity
- Market dynamics
- Market share and position
- Definition of products or services
- Identification of potential beneficiaries, users, and clients

IP and Knowledge Management Strategy

The StretchBio approach is, to the extent of the current literature survey, novel and, thus, offers possibilities for intellectual protection. Furthermore, there does not exist any limiting previous IP from any of the partners of the consortium.

According to the Consortium Agreement (CA) made effective on the 1st of May 2021, results are owned by the Party that generates them. The CA is based upon the DESCA (Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement) model consortium agreement and includes provisions for results, access rights, and non-disclosure of information, among others.

The creation of a technology-based spin-off company with the participation of one or more partners of the consortium will also be assessed as one of many strategies to protect and share results and commercial exits.

Pending a detailed IPR Analysis and Knowledge Management Plan, an initial patent search in [Espacenet](#) revealed over 200 patents close to the field at hand, thus the consortium has budgeted 5.000€ for an external patentability study that will determine freedom to operate.

Besides seeking professional legal advice, the consortium will also make use of the [European IP Helpdesk](#), a first-line IP service providing free-of-charge support to help European SMEs and beneficiaries of EU-funded research projects manage their IP. The Helpdesk continuously streams [events](#) to help beneficiaries understand the IP landscape and showcase examples of success stories.

Networking with Other Projects and Initiatives

The objective of this activity is to establish solid synergies with other projects and initiatives in the oncology field. To achieve this, participation in joint events and workshops will be promoted.

The consortium will make use of the [Enterprise Europe Network](#) portal, which provides an opportunity to connect with experts and businesses if an international scale-up is required.

Exploitation and Business Plan Creation

The exploitation plan is the strategy and process that allow the capitalization of the tangible and intangible results of the StretchBio project, optimizing their value, enhancing their impact, and facilitating their integration at multiple levels.

Initially, the consortium agrees on the main results to be obtained from the project, happening in a time frame that goes beyond the project's duration:

Joint or individual start-ups have not been considered at this stage, given the prematurity of any results, but will be analysed in future reviews if required.

Taking the partner's inputs into consideration, the business plan will consider:

- Market analysis
- Business strategy
- Operations plan
- Competitor identification and analysis
- Clear action plan

Start-up operations, estimation of time to market, investors, and additional funding will also be included in the report, if required.

ReadyCell, as leader of the current WP, will use the [Horizon Results Booster](#) Service 2 for tailor-made training and support to develop the business plan.

Access to Different Funding Schemes

According to the exploitation strategy defined by each partner, a portfolio of private and public funding sources and the need to create spin-offs or start-ups will be identified to allow further growth.

Support schemes for follow-up steps will also be considered if required, such as regional and national programmes, [EU Health Programme](#), or [EIC Prizes](#). If the results demonstrate an impact on society, the consortium will also consider applying for the [Horizon Impact Award](#).

Project Gantt chart and High-level Schedule of Exploitation Actions

Figure 4 - Exploitation Roadmap

6 Annex

Visual Guidelines

STRETCHbio

Logo & Brand Identity Guidelines

1	Logo Specifics
2	Clear space
3	Logo variation
4	Colour Specifications
5	Typography in Use
6	Logo Best Practices
7	Pattern and elements

Logomark

the logo is the face of STRETCHbio - the primary visual expression that will be used to identify the project, meaning that we need to be careful to use it correctly and to do so consistently.

Primary Logomark

Clear space

Clear space prevents type, imagery or other graphic elements from interfering with the legibility of the logo. No graphic elements should encroach the border around the logomark. This space is determined by the height of the "o".

Logo variation

STRETCHbio logo used on an application will often depend on the background and production method. When using the logo on a white background you can use full color version logo.

Full color

Full color with background

One color

One color : Reverse

Primary colors

CMYK	87 51 29 14	48 16 15 1
HEX	#236585	#64B4C8
PANTONE	647C	644C
CMYK	9 40 84 1	0 0 0 0
HEX	#E29E43	#FFFFFF
PANTONE	647C	BLANC

The Typeface Family

Hammersmith One Regular and Roboto Mono.

When to Use:

Hammersmith One Regular is the primary font used for the logo wording. It should only be used in the logo.

Hammersmith One Regular
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@£\$%^&*()

When to Use:

Roboto Mono is to be used for all other forms of standard body text, ranging from: stationery, website design, brochures and all forms of general documents.

Roboto
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
Z abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@£\$%^&*()

Do Not: Logomark

Do not resize or change the position of the logomark.

Do Not: Fonts

Do not use any other font, no matter how close it might look to Nexa

Do Not: Sizing

Do not use squish or squash the logo. Any resizing must be in proportion.

Do Not: Colour

Do not change the colours even if they look similar. Use the official colour specifications detailed in these guidelines

Pattern

Pattern is one of the main elements in STRECHbio brand identity. It is intended to be repeatable to be used in wide variety of applications. Our inspiration comes from the pilar element.

Single elements

These three elements represent the living tissue samples, the laser and the nanopillars at the compact nanosystem. The three elements are intended to be used as small decorative items.

